

TESSE²B
the smart energy storage

Thermal Energy Storage Systems for Energy Efficient Buildings

Final Workshop/B2B Meeting

**PORTUGAL
18 SEPTEMBER 2019**

MORE INFO:

<http://www.tesse2b.eu>

Last opportunity to know TESSE2b solution!
Join us at **Polytechnic Institute of Setúbal** and participate in this event with national and regional representatives from industry and academia.
JOIN US!

Visit our website and find out more information about this innovative project.

[visit website](http://www.tesse2b.eu)

CINEA - ENA CONFERENCE

The workshop will be preceded by **CINEA-ENA 1st Setúbal International Conference on Energy and Sustainability** (17 September), promoted by **IPS Research Center for Energy and Environment (CINEA)**, in partnership with **Arrábida Energy and Environment Agency (ENA)**. With the participation of TESSe2b partners, the event will be a privileged meeting point for all professionals and entities in the sector.

MORE INFO:

<http://www.tesse2b.eu/>

<https://investigacao.ips.pt/cinea>

http://www.si.ips.pt/ips_si/noticias_geral.ver_noticia...

